

COMPLEX GEODETIC SURVEYS OF THE ARGENTINE ISLANDS ARCHIPELAGO WITHIN THE SEASON OF THE 29th UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC EXPEDITION

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Complex geodetic surveys of the Argentine Islands archipelago, Antarctica, within the framework of the season of the 29th Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition, include a number of tasks:

- conducting precision GNSS measurements at the points of the Argentine Islands archipelago geodynamic polygon to investigate modern crustal movements;
- replacement of the temporary GNSS receiver of the ASAV continuous operating station;
- installation and testing of an autonomous continuous operating GNSS station for continuous monitoring of modern crustal movements;
- monitoring of changes in island glaciers by aerial survey with UAVs and satellite radar interferometry;
- creation of orthophotographic images of the islands adjacent to the Akademik Vernadsky station.

Monitoring of modern crustal movements in the area of the Argentine Islands archipelago, in particular, the study of tectonic fault activity and spatial deformations affecting the stability of the Earth's surface and geospheric processes. Geodynamic studies of modern crustal movements using GNSS methods are a continuation of previous studies carried out as part of seasonal Ukrainian expeditions in 2002, 2005, 2008, 2013, 2014, 2018, and 2019. Within the framework of the season of the 29th Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition, four new points were established, the points of the geodynamic polygon in the area of the Argentine Islands archipelago were updated, and a cycle of GNSS observations was carried out, including repeated measurements at 21 points.

The temporary GNSS receiver of the ASAV continuous operating station installed in 2019 was replaced with a Trimble R9s GNSS receiver with Trimble Zephyr 3 Base antenna purchased by the National Academy of Sciences. Another autonomous permanent GNSS station equipped with solar panels for constant power supply and further testing was also installed.

The study of the mechanisms of changes in the Antarctic ice sheet, in particular, changes in the volume of glaciers adjacent to the Akademik Vernadsky station, includes the influence of both climatic and geodynamic factors. A comparison of the aerial survey results with similar data obtained in 2019 provides an opportunity to accurately assess the difference in the volume of ice cover on individual islands. In addition, the joint processing of aerial survey results with satellite radar interferometry data, which is a remote sensing technology based on satellite radar images, allows us to analyze the spatial and temporal changes occurring on large mainland glaciers.

The last completed task was to create new and update existing cartographic materials for certain parts of the Argentine Islands archipelago. For this purpose, aerial surveys were conducted from UAV, and precision plan-altitude georeferencing of the images was performed using differential GNSS measurements.

Complex geodetic surveys of the Argentine Islands archipelago during the season of the 29th Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition allow us to assess the current movements of the Earth's crust within the Penola Strait – Lemaire Channel, to accumulate and analyze satellite measurements at the permanent GNSS station ASAV and the autonomous GNSS station, to estimate the extent of changes in the ice cover of island glaciers and to update the orthophotographic images of the islands adjacent to the Akademik Vernadsky station.